

Hypergeometric Differential Equation for Klein Gordon Excited State

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In the literature, the NU (Nikiforov-Uvarov) method is frequently used to obtain solutions in terms of Rodrigues polynomials of the Klein Gordon equation for certain potentials. In particular, in (1) this method is used to solve the Klein Gordon bound equation for equal scalar and vector potentials, with the common potential being equal to $V_1 \operatorname{sech}^2(q(x)) + V_2 \tanh(q(x))$ i.e. the Rosen Morse potential. ($\operatorname{sech}(x)$ and $\tanh(x)$ are defined later.)

In a previous note, we argued one may write the wavefunction as $W(x) = W_0(x)D_n(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction. This leads to a coupled differential equation for $D_n(x)$ and $d/dx W_0(x) / W_0(x)$ with the potential removed and a factor of 1 in front of $-d/dx d/dx D_n(x)$. Depending on the form of $d/dx W_0 / W_0$, this DE may be of a form allowing for a Rodrigues polynomial solution. From math theories (2), a second order polynomial factor for $-d/dx d/dx D_n(x)$ is allowed so as in (3), one may consider transformations $s=g(x)$ which yield such a second order polynomial. One may then verify if the factor of the transformed $2 d/dx D_n(x) d/dx W_0 / W_0$ yields a linear polynomial. If it does, one may write a Rodrigues polynomial solution. In this note, we apply this approach to the Rosen Morse potential.

General Method

The bound state Klein Gordon equation for equal scalar and vector potentials ($V(x)$) is given in (1) by:

$$-d/dx d/dx W(x) - 2(E+M) V(x) W(x) = E_b E_b W(x) \text{ where } E_b E_b = E E - m_0^2 \quad ((1))$$

We consider a solution of the form $W(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state solution (or at least a full solution). Then the remaining coupled equation is:

$$- d/dx d/dx W_1(x) - 2 d/dx W_1(x) [d/dx W_0(x)/W_0(x)] = [-E_b^0 E_b^0 + E_b E_b] W_1(x) \quad ((2))$$

In order to have a Rodrigues polynomial solution, (2) one must have a DE of the form:

$$p(x) d/dx d/dx W_1(x) + q(x) d/dx W_1(x) + \text{constant } W_1(x) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Where $p(x)$ is at most quadratic and $q(x)$ linear. Equation ((2)) satisfies these criteria if $d/dx W_0(x)/W_0(x)$ is a linear polynomial, i.e. $ax+b$, with a and b constants. The next issue is to link $d/dx W_0 / W_0$ to the potential. One has the identity:

$$d/dx [d/dx W_0(x) / W_0] = [d/dx d/dx W_0(x)] / W_0(x) - [d/dx W_0 / W_0]^2 \quad ((4))$$

From ((1)), one has: $[d/dx d/dx W_0(x) / W_0(x)] = -2(E+M) V(x) - E_b E_b$, ((5)) thus one may use $dW_0/dx / W_0 = ax+b$ in ((4)) and the expression ((5)) in ((4)) to solve for a and b if one knows the potential. Alternatively, one may find the form of a potential compatible with the $ax+b$ form for $d/dx W_0/W_0$. Another approach is to integrate $d/dx \ln(W_0) = ax+b$ and then apply this to the Klein Gordon equation.

Transformations

Equation ((2)) is not the most general form, i.e. it is not ((3)), because the factor of $d/dx d/dx W(x)$ is -1 and not $p(x)$ a quadratic polynomial. One may consider transformations $s=g(x)$ which yield a quadratic polynomial (in s) factor for $d/ds d/ds W_1(x)$. This forces the factor of $d/dx W_1(x)$ to be a linear polynomial, which places restrictions on $d/ds W_0(s) / W_0(s)$.

Consider the Rosen Morse potential as done in (1)

$$V(x) = -V_1 \operatorname{sech}^2(x) - V_2 \tanh(x) \quad ((6))$$

Here $\tanh(x) = [\exp(x) - q \exp(-x)] / [\exp(x) + q \exp(-x)]$ and $\operatorname{sech}(x) = 1 / [\exp(x) + q \exp(-x)]$

As in (1), consider a transformation $s=\tanh(x)$. Then:

$$ds/dx = 2s \quad \text{and} \quad 1-s^2 = 2q \operatorname{sech}^2(x) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, ((2)) becomes:

$$4s^2 d/ds d/ds W_0(s) + (4s - 2s^2) [d/ds W_0/W_0] d/ds W_0 = (E_b^2 - E_b^2) W_0(s) \quad ((8))$$

The factor of $d/ds d/ds W_0(s)$ is quadratic so the factor of $d/ds W_0(s)$ must be linear i.e.:

$$d/ds W_0 / W_0 = [as+b] / 2s(2-s) \quad ((9))$$

[One could integrate to solve for $W_0(s)$ at this point, in terms of a and b, the unknowns, but we use an alternative approach.]

Consider ((4)) with s used instead of x

$$d/ds [d/ds W_0(s) / W_0] = [d/ds d/ds W_0(s)] / W_0(s) - [d/ds W_0 / W_0]^2 \quad ((10))$$

Now ((1)) becomes:

$$-4s^2 d/ds d/ds W_0(s) - 4s d/ds W_0(x) - 2(E+M) V(s) W_0(s) = E_b E_b W(s) \quad ((11))$$

$V(s)$ from ((6)) is given by $-V_1 2q (1-s*s) -V_2 s$

The question becomes: Is it possible to satisfy ((9)) i.e find values for a and b ?

Using ((1)):

$$\frac{a}{[2s(2-s)]} - \frac{(as+b)(4-4s)}{[2s(2-s)]^2} = -\left[\frac{(as+b)}{[2s(2-s)]^2} + \frac{1}{4s*s} \right] \{-4s (as+b)/[2s(2-s)] - 2(E+M)[-V_1 2q (1-s*s) -V_2 s] - E_{bo}E_{bo}\}$$

One may try to equate coefficients of s in order to find solutions of a and b . For example, Let $B=2(E+M)(-V_1 2q)$. Then

$$\text{Coefficient of } s*s*s*s \text{ is: } 3a = -12B -4E_{bo}E_{bo} +16V_2 \text{ (solve for } a)$$

$$\text{Coefficient of } s*s*s \text{ is: } -5b = 2ab -4a -16V_2 -16B +16E_{bo}E_{bo}$$

$$\text{Coefficient of } s*s \text{ is: } 0 = -b*b +16B -16E_{bo}E_{bo} \text{ (solve for } b)$$

The first and third factors can be used to solve for a and b , but these values must be compatible with the coefficient of $s*s*s$. The equations contain the ground state energy E_{bo} .

If the results are compatible, one has a Rodrigues solution. In (1), the NU method is used to also find Rodrigues polynomial solutions. More details are given in (1).

Alternatively, one may use $d/ds \ln(W_0) = (as+b)/(4s-2s*s)$ and integrate to find a solution for $W_0(s)$. This may then be used in ((2)) directly.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to apply to write $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state solution, to try to simplify the Klein Gordon bound state equation. This leads to a coupled equation ((2)) for $W_1(x)$ and $d/dx W_0/W_0$. Math theory indicates the coefficient of $d/dx d/dx W_1(x)$ may be quadratic and that for $d/dx W_1(x)$ linear in x in order for Rodrigues polynomials to serve as a solution. Equation ((2)) has a factor of -1 for $d/dx d/dx W_1(x)$ so one may consider transformations $s=g(x)$ which lead to $(as*s+bs +c) d/ds d/ds W_1(s)$ provided the coefficient of $d/W/ds$ remain linear. This imposes restrictions on $dW_0/ds (ds/dx)$. We use ((10)) to link dW_0/dx with the scalar=vector potential $V(s)$ to see if one may find a compatible solution. In this note, it seems one may be able to find a compatible solution for the Rosen-Morse potential. In (1), the NU method is used to find the solution to this same problem.

References

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